

RISEEnergy

**Research Infrastructure Services
for Renewable Energy**

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D3.2 - "Use cases and lists of existing metadata platforms and data repositories"

Work Package 3 - Cross cutting and RES RI-Services to support technologies, systems and policy makers

Task 3.3 - Metadata service along the value chain

Due date of deliverable: 28 February 2025

Actual submission date: 28 February 2025

Project Acronym	RISEnergy
Call	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01
Grant Agreement No.	101131793
Project Start Date	01-03-2024
Project End Date	31-08-2028
Duration	54 months

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INFORMATION

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Reviewed by	Mike Hayes (TYN UCC) Thomas Strasser (AIT)	2025-02-05 2025-02-13
Approved by	General Assembly	2025-02-24
Approved by	Olga Suminska-Ebersoldt, Deputy Coordinator	2025-02-28
Status	Final	2025-02-28

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

SEN	Sensitive	
CL	Classified	
PU	Public	x

VERSIONS

Date	Version	Author	Signature	Comment
06-11-24	0.0	S. Nakamae	SN	The first draft on ToC
31-01-25	0.1	S. Nakamae, K. Malek & K. Heussen		More contents
05-02-25	0.2	S. Nakamae	SN	Table (added incomplete)
14-02-25	0.3	S. Nakamae	SN	Executive summary
24-02-25	0.4	S. Müller	SM	Small Layout adaptation
28-02-25	1.0	O.Sumiska-Ebersoldt	OSE	Final

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

RISEnergy is an EU-funded project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101131793.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CAS	Chemical Abstract Service
CC	Creative Commons
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
CSV	Comma-separated value
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EERA	European Energy Research Alliance
EIRIE	European Interconnection for Research Innovation & Entrepreneurship
EMMO	Elementary Multiperspective Materials Ontology
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format, Version 5
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IP	Intellectual Property
ICSD	Identified Crystal Structures Database
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MD	Metadata
METAS	Federal Institute of Metrology
MPID	mParticle ID
NOMAD	Novel Materials Discovery
ORD	Open Research Data
PID	Persistent IDentifiers
PV	Photovoltaics
RE	Renewal Energy
RI	Research Infrastructure
STE	Solar Thermal Electricity
TA	Transnational Access
TL	Task Leaders
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D3.2 - Use Cases and Lists of Existing Metadata Platforms and Data Repositories, summarizes the scientific data management strategy of the RISEnergy project, focusing on metadata services that support the efficient sharing, interoperability, and usability of research data. This document is complementary to Deliverable D3.1 - Scientific Data Guideline and Deliverable D5.2 - Data Management Plan (DMP). Together, these reports establish a comprehensive approach to managing scientific data and metadata within the project's Transnational Access (TA) and Virtual Access (VA) research infrastructures in accordance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles.

This deliverable reports current metadata and data management practices within RISEnergy's research infrastructures, identifying challenges and best practices. The report also provides structured lists of existing metadata platforms and data repositories relevant to RISEnergy's renewable energy technology areas. The gap analysis revealed that while some RISEnergy partners have structured metadata practices, the vast majority lack standardized frameworks. To address this, the report outlines the next steps in RISEnergy's metadata strategy that includes the development of standardized metadata templates and a searchable database of metadata and data repositories. These efforts will streamline short and long-term data usability in either the data workflow or data sharing context. By implementing of these metadata services, RISEnergy aims to facilitate collaborations between researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers creating a more integrated and efficient research ecosystem within the renewable energy technology sector.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The project RISEnergy (*Research infrastructure services to enable Research & Innovation (R&I) addressing main challenges and EU priorities* <https://risenergy-project.eu/>) aims to foster a long-term, coordinated research effort among leading private companies and research institutions to identify and promote ways to accelerate renewable energy (RE) technologies and systems, Technology Readiness Level (TRL) progression & system integration. The three key activities of RISEnergy are:

1. Access to outstanding research infrastructures (RIs)
2. Access to cross-RI services
3. Access to proactive innovation management

RISEnergy boasts an extensive Transnational Access (TA) programme, encompassing 84 TAs RIs covering all target areas of renewable energy technologies, together with three Virtual Access (VA) RIs in its portfolio. The energy technology areas covered are Photovoltaics (PV), Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)/Solar Thermal Energy (STE), Hydrogen, Biofuels, Offshore Wind, Ocean Energy, Integrated Grids and Energy Storage, as well as two cross-cutting areas, Materials Research and Information and Communication Technologies (ICT).

Success of long-term, collaborative research require timely and correct transmission of results (i.e., data) among the stakeholders. RISEnergy has outlined a comprehensive data management strategy (data management plan, (DMP) cf. Deliverable D5.2) for its RIs and the users, in line with the findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) principles. Indeed, mutually agreed strategic decisions on data management; i.e., data organization and storage, file naming conventions and metadata collection are essential for **facilitating data sharing** (improved access and usability) between RIs and users, while also for accelerating knowledge transfer along the innovation chain (or through dissemination) by **streamlining data pipeline**. In both of these contexts, proper collection and documentation of all relevant **metadata** are crucial in order to avoid loss of information and/or misinterpretations. In this regard, RISEnergy aims is to *create metadata structures along the value chain from materials and devices to frameworks and systems to help the RIs and the users find the most suitable metadata schemata to support FAIR data management.*

The present deliverable is the first step toward this objective. It comprises of following elements:

- Section 2: Summary of Scientific Data management strategy including the overview of metadata services provided within RISEnergy
- Section 3: Metadata and data management use case examples among RISEnergy RIs and the best practices found in RES platforms with Gap analysis
- Section 4: Existing data and metadata repositories and their purposes
- Section 5: Future direction - Classification of Metadata templates
- Section 6: Conclusion & Recommendations

Deliverable D3.2 therefore defines the roadmap on the metadata service most adapted for the RISEnergy members tailored for their vast renewable energy applications.

2. SCIENTIFIC DATA AND METADATA MANAGEMENT STRATEGY OF RISENERGY

2.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP, D5.2)

2.1.1 Overview of the data handling requirements in RISEnergy

RISEnergy follows Horizon Europe FAIR guidelines¹ and EU GDPR² regulations. The detailed guidelines on how to implement an effective data management strategy in line with the FAIR principles are defined in the DMP, i.e., Deliverable D5.2. The DMP describes the Open Science (open access) approach on how the data is collected, generated and handled (exploitation, curation, preservation, etc.) within RISEnergy in line with Article 17 of the Grant Agreement (GA), for both *scientific publications* and *research data*.

In regards to the research data, it is stipulated that "*the beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles.*" This requirement outlines the following:

- Establishing a DMP to be updated regularly.
- Submission of the data in a *trusted repository*³ as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP.
- Ensuring open access⁴ (via the repository) to the deposited data through a Creative Commons licensing (e.g., CC0, CC-BY, etc.) as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP.
- Providing information (via the repository) about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

In addition, *Metadata* (MD) associated with deposited data must also be open "*under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following:*"

- Datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo);
- Horizon Europe or Euratom funding;
- Grant project name, acronym and number;
- Licensing terms;

¹ HORIZON EUROPE FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TEMPLATE

² Guidelines to FAIR data management in Horizon Europe and the GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)

³ If required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements

⁴ Accessibility follows the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular: 1) be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or 2) be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP

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- Persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant;
- Persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs (where applicable).

2.1.2 Data types collected in RISEnergy

Data within RISEnergy comprises not only scientific data but also documents (e.g., reports, presentations, agreements) and knowledge (e.g., IP, data security protocol and process flows). Categories of data generated within RISEnergy are defined as:

- TA/VA data
 - Technical and personal data;
 - Scientific data;
 - Computer codes, algorithms, flowcharts;
 - Process know-how;
 - Reports and questionnaires;
- Scientific publications/presentations/patents;
- Data collected using surveys, feedback forms, and questionnaires;
- Non-TA/VA-related personal data;
- Technical data and reports/publications;
- Modelling data, developed algorithms, tools, methodology, and software;
- Sustainability assessment data.

2.2 CROSS-RI SERVICE ON SCIENTIFIC DATA AND METADATA

As an integral part of the comprehensive cross-RI services, RISEnergy offers data/metadata handling tools and guidances to its members (researchers and RIs) through two *Tasks; Framework for Digital Services and Digital Twins* and *Metadata services along the value chain*. The **DMP** (Deliverable D5.2), the Deliverable D3.1 "**Scientific data guideline**" and the present Deliverable D3.2 outline the **scientific data management strategy** for the RISEnergy project, based upon which metadata service tools will be developed (Deliverable D3.6 "Searchable database on data repositories and metadata platforms with metadata templates"). While Deliverable D3.1's focus is on **FAIRification** for ensuring the effective collection, management, and dissemination of data within the project to support innovation in line with the **FAIR principles**, Deliverable D3.2 is concerned by the organization methodologies of data and metadata.

These guidances and tools will assist RISEnergy members to easily create metadata structures along the value chain for their **scientific digital artefacts**.

2.2.1 Summary of Scientific Data Guideline

Types of data concerned by Deliverable D3.1, which are common to the "metadata services," are classified as follows. For each category, a short data-type/source description and a summary of guidelines are outlined.

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Table 1: Types of data collected in RISEnergy

type	Description & Guideline
Scientific data:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Description:</i> Data collected from TA and VA activities. This data includes that generated/collected during the research stay of Users within the TA/VA. If relevant, some previously generated data may also be re-used by the User • <i>Guideline:</i> Use trusted repositories' open access with persistent identifiers, rich metadata and licensing to ensure FAIR compliance and reproducibility. Use institutional repositories where required.
Computer codes/algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Description:</i> Codes, algorithms, and workflows developed within the project • <i>Guideline:</i> Managed in repositories like GitHub for reproducibility ensuring transparency and reproducibility. Implement version control mechanisms to track modifications, and standardized documentation accompanies all digital artefacts. <p>The project emphasizes interoperability, ensuring that codes are stored in machine-readable formats, such as Python, C++, and MATLAB. Where possible, codes are linked with sustainability assessment tools and energy models to enable broader reuse and integration.</p>
Publications and presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Description:</i> Research outputs - Scientific publications, conference presentations, and patents • <i>Guideline:</i> Store in openly accessible repositories (e.g., Zenodo) unless restricted by IP concerns. Use institutional repositories to provide additional storage. <p>Metadata should accompany all publications, ensuring discoverability and proper attribution. Use Creative Commons licensing frameworks, (e.g., CC-BY) to support data reuse while maintaining appropriate authorship recognition</p>
Dissemination/education, financial and administrative data and sustainability assessments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Description:</i> examples - training materials, educational content, workshop recordings, and financial or administrative reports; Surveys, interviews, literature reviews. • <i>Guideline:</i> Store in trusted repositories (public and/or internal) using standard formats with metadata for accessibility, interoperability and reuse under controlled access/open licenses. Make use of existing sustainability databases and ontologies (e.g., Elementary Multiperspective Materials Ontology)

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	(EMMO) ⁵ , Mindful Materials (MM) ⁶ , Materials Data Science Ontology ⁷ Open Energy Ontology (OEO) ⁸) to structure metadata assessing the technical, economic, environmental, and social impacts (Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)).
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FAIR compliance and validation:

The following methodologies are to be adopted for ensuring the FAIR-compliant compliance of collected data.

- **Findability:** Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are assigned to datasets, accompanied by (rich) metadata following widely accepted standards (e.g., DCAT-AP, JSON-LD) for efficient recovery.
- **Accessibility:** Trusted open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo) are used whenever possible (*"as open as possible, as closed as necessary"*) to ensure wide availability⁹. *Restricted datasets* are securely stored in RISEnergy SharePoint (project's online collaboration platform) with strict access control. Partners institutional repositories should also be used whenever required.
- **Interoperability:** Data is formatted using such as **JSON-LD, CSV, and OWL** to enhance integration across platforms and domains.
- **Reusability:** Licensing models (e.g., **CC-BY**) and metadata documentation ensure that datasets remain reusable by the wider scientific community.

⁵ <https://emmo-repo.github.io/>

⁶ <https://www.mindfulmaterials.com/connected-data>

⁷ <https://matportal.org/ontologies/MDS>

⁸ <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/>

⁹ The RISEnergy consortium also intends to collaborate with the European Interconnection for Research Innovation & Entrepreneurship (EIRIE) platform (<https://ses.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eirie/en>) which is a meeting point for all actors active in the field of energy R&I from all Europe.

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FAIR assessment tools such as the FAIR Data Maturity Model¹⁰, OpenAIRE Validator¹¹, EERAdat FAIR toolbox¹², FZJ's METADOR¹³ and ARDC¹⁴ should be used for validating the FAIR data practices.

Open Science Principles Adoption in Scientific Data

In adopting of open science principles, i.e., ensuring that data remains widely available for verification and reuse, a structured ontology framework is needed to **standardize metadata definitions** across research domains. Once the ontology has been defined, a recommended method for continued application of the open science principles is to develop a community-based **FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP)**. An example **questionnaire** is given for documenting FAIR principle compliancy check, ensuring that all research datasets meet the necessary **metadata, licensing, and security requirements** (See Deliverable D3.1 for detailed explanation) either in the data workflow (Extract-Transform-Load) or in the data sharing (repository submission, publication, etc) contexts.

2.2.2 Metadata services - Current practice

The RISEnergy RIs house diverse datasets generated by various instruments and methodologies both experimental and numerical, creating challenges for standardization, interoperability, and reusability. A dedicated task is created precisely to tackle this challenge; i.e., to assist RISEnergy RIs and users by providing robust *but flexible* metadata services, including standardized templates and workflow design examples. Such services help researchers to describe their data efficiently and consistently; i.e., easily shared, discovered, and integrated across disciplines and infrastructures¹⁵, ultimately accelerating innovation in renewable energy technologies extending far beyond the duration of the project.

To achieve this goal, the following approach is undertaken:

- Collection of use cases from RISEnergy RIs: By examining different use cases, the project aim to identify the specific metadata needs of our partners, tailoring solutions that enhance the overall efficiency and impact of the research ecosystem via metadata standardization and data handling automation. (part of the present deliverable);

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg/outputs/?output=94566>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5541132>

¹² <https://eeradata-platform.eu/platform/>

¹³ <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/ias-9/news-and-events/news/new-tool-metador>

¹⁴ <https://ardc.edu.au/resource-hub/making-data-fair/>

¹⁵ The proposed metadata schemas shall align with the RISEnergy's DMP (D5.2) and adhere to the FAIR principles as outlined in D3.1 and summarized in Section 1.

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- Collection of metadata practices in RES platforms (ongoing work);
- Gap analysis;
- Creation of metadata templates for RISEnergy RIs and users: These templates will facilitate the curation and organization of user-produced data for their submission to suitable open-data repositories;
- Collection of existing metadata platforms/data repositories (included in the present deliverable) on materials, devices and systems relevant to the 8 RES technologies of RISEnergy and creation of searchable database (i.e., Deliverable D3.6)

For a large-scale and interdisciplinary/intersectoral project such as RISEnergy, MD services serve as the backbone of collaborative efforts, bridging gaps between diverse research domains, facilitating seamless data exchange, and ultimately accelerating innovation in RE technologies.

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3. CURRENT MD MANAGEMENT PRACTICE WITHIN RISENERGY TA & VA RIs

As specified in Article 17 of the RISEnergy GA, the beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action responsibly in line with the FAIR principles, while protecting the members' IP interests by following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary. Members need well-organized MD structure for comply to this obligation at all levels of openness, from TA/VA access reporting to RISEnergy, to submitting data to open repositories, and publishing results in scientific journals.

Broadly speaking, within the RISEnergy community the MD structuring and use is needed for two main reasons (user story):

- MD for data sharing
 - Ensures that datasets are **FAIR** .
 - Typically includes **descriptive MD**, such as dataset title, authors, formats, licensing, and persistent identifiers (PIDs).
 - Supports **external discoverability**, enabling integration with repositories such as **Zenodo** and **B2-Find**.
 - **FAIR principles explicitly require provenance metadata**, which connects it to data pipeline metadata:
 - **Findability (F3)**: MD must include provenance information to ensure dataset traceability.
 - **Reusability (R1.2)**: MD should describe dataset lineage, transformations, and applied processes to support reuse.
- MD for data pipelines
 - Tracks how data flows through **processing workflows**.
 - Describes **provenance, transformations, versioning, dependencies**, and data processing steps.
 - Supports **automation, reproducibility, and internal workflow management**.

It is possible to distinguish these two stories as: Data sharing metadata primarily ensures that datasets adhere to FAIR principles by providing descriptive elements. In contrast, data pipeline metadata documents how data moves through processing workflows, capturing information on transformations, dependencies, validation, and execution logs. This metadata supports workflow automation, reproducibility, and traceability. Although these metadata serve different functions, they share common elements, particularly in provenance tracking, as required by R1.2 (Reusability) and F3 (Findability). Consequently, a FAIR-compliant metadata system must include provenance elements, making workflow metadata a part of the data-sharing infrastructure. It is therefore possible—but not required—to implement a single metadata model that serves both data sharing and data pipeline tracking. One such example is demonstrated in the METAS case study presented in Deliverable D3.1.

With this in mind, 2-step survey was launched soliciting use cases of structured metadata and data applications from RISEnergy's 84 RIs as the first step toward building a

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comprehensive and flexible MD services for the project members. The initial survey consisted of three simple questions on; RI's experimental/numerical platform, Connection to existing data platforms (or not) and Use (or planned use) of structured metadata scheme (or not).

Less than 10 RIs self-identified themselves as having ongoing or planned MD structures. These RIs received the second and more detailed survey, collecting following information:

- **Title:** Description of RI offered within RISEnergy - please correct if inaccurate
- **User Story:** MD for 1) data exchange or 2) data pipeline
- **Stakeholders:** Data source, provider/host and target users
- **Objectives:** short description of how MD is used
- **Operational Context classification:** Management, Lab processes, Operation, Experimental/Simulation data Other
- **RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas:** to choose from 8 RE technology areas of RISEnergy
- **Data Characteristics:** On datasets and presentation
- **Metadata requirements:** To choose from a list of common MD types

In the next section, we report on the responses received from the 6 RI (TAs and VAs), each respondent completing a table with bespoke questions and provided detailed explanations.

3.1 CURRENT MD MANAGEMENT PRACTICE WITHIN RISENERGY TA & VA

The MD practices vary significantly among the 6 RIs who responded to the survey—not only in the types of data and metadata collected, their formats, and intended purposes, but also in the level of metadata readiness. This diversity reflects the broad range of approaches and maturity levels in metadata management across respondents.

Table 2: MD use case: METAS Station at Plataforma Solar de Almeria

Category	Short description	Additional comment
Title	Continuous collection and sharing of environmental observation data: METAS use case	
Use Case ID	Do not fill (internal use only)	
User Story - primary	Metadata for data sharing (Open & FAIR) aims to facilitate sharing across Research Infrastructures (RIs), ensuring attribution, interpretability, findability, and reproducibility of datasets	It includes structured descriptions, persistent identifiers, and adherence to standards like DCAT-AP2 and JSON-LD
User Story - secondary	Metadata for data pipelines ensures structured workflow management and traceability by tracking data transformations and dependencies. It maintains consistency, supports reproducibility, and enables interoperability within METAS' FAIRification process.	
Stakeholders: Data source	METAS station at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), responsible for collecting, processing, and maintaining solar radiation and atmospheric datasets	
Stakeholders: Data provider and host	CIEMAT-PSA	
Stakeholders: Target users	researchers, engineers, and policymakers in solar energy, atmospheric science and renewable energy sectors	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure FAIR compliance by structuring and standardizing metadata for solar radiation and atmospheric datasets. • Improve data interoperability across research infrastructures through standardized metadata models (DCAT-AP2, JSON-LD). • Facilitate data accessibility and sharing via open repositories and cloud-based platforms (e.g., EGI DataHub). • Enhance reproducibility and traceability by integrating provenance information into the metadata framework. 	
Primary Operational Context	Experimental/Simulation data (physical units, chemical compositions, measurement quality, etc.)	FAIR-compliant management of solar radiation and atmospheric data, supporting data sharing, interoperability, and reuse within research infrastructures and open science platforms
Secondary Operational Context	Experimental/Simulation data (physical units, chemical compositions, measurement quality, etc.)	Integration of metadata into data pipelines to support automated processing, reproducibility, and workflow traceability within renewable energy research.
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (primary)	Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)/ Solar Thermal Electricity (STE),	
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (secondary)	Other	Several Renewable Energy sectors are concerned

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Data Characteristics: dataset	High-resolution solar radiation and atmospheric datasets, including raw sensor measurements and processed data with calibration and quality control applied.		
Data Characteristics: presentation	data: CSV / metadata in JSON-LD format		
Metadata requirements - check all that apply	General Information (e.g. identification of authorship)	x	Includes dataset authorship, contributors, and affiliations
	Traceable identifier	x	B2Handle PiDs assigned to datasets
	Dataset Details (e.g. data source, time-span)	x	Covers dataset origin, collection period, and resolution
	Data source context (e.g. sensor locations, application assets, facility, etc.)	x	Includes sensor specifications, location, and calibration details.
	Data processing	x	Describes transformations, validation, and quality control applied.
	Instrumentation, equipment description	x	Metadata on pyranometers, pyrhemeters, LIDAR, and other sensors.
	Experiment identification: experiment details (e.g. scope-definition, Techniques, Material Name, Environmental Conditions, software used)	x	No specific experimental design beyond continuous data collection.
	File and data format	x	CSV / JSON-LD
	Permalink	x	Zenodo, B2-HANDLE
	Workflow information	x	provenance, transformation, versions, dependencies
	Quality Assurance		Not requested, but it is internal and performed before ingestion to final database
	Access and Licensing (e.g. local, organization server, cloud, public. License, Access Rights, Instructions)	x	Cloud, Defined access rights, licensing terms, and storage locations
	Resources	x	RISEnergy TA access funding
FAIR-Compliance	x	Metadata aligned with FAIR principles	
Other			

Table 3: MD use case: FastBlade at University of Edinburgh

Category	Short description	Additional comment
Title	FastBlade	A custom-built NI distributed data logging system, synchronised across a time-sensitive network. All sensors, calibrations and logged data are recorded into TDMS data files.
UC-ID	Do not fill (internal use only)	
User Story - primary	Metadata for data pipelines (emphasis of semantic interoperability/ontologies, syntactic correctness)	AMS Acta that is the institutional open access repository
User Story - secondary		
Stakeholders: Data source	Lab Experiments	
Stakeholders: Data provider and host	Research Institution and Industry	
Stakeholders: Target users	other researchers, Industry, Standards bodies (IEC)	
Objectives	Operation (example: measurement and SCADA, ICT logs.. How the data aquisition system and infrastructure are operated)	
Primary Operational Context	Experimental/Simulation data (physical units, chemical compositions, measurement quality, etc.)	
Secondary Operational Context		
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (primary)	Ocean Energy	
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (secondary)	Materials Science	
Data Characteristics: dataset	rawdata, processed data, software generated, raw image, processed images, audio signals, calibration data, sensor location data (daq channel and physical location)	
Data Characteristics: presentation	TDMS, xlsx, TIFF, WAV, and software specific	
Metadata requirements - check all that apply	General Information (e.g. identification of authorship)	x
	Traceable identifier	x

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Dataset Details (e.g. data source, time-span)	x	
Data source context (e.g. sensor locations, application assets, facility, etc.)	x	
Data processing	x	
Instrumentation, equipment description	x	
Experiment identification: experiment details (e.g. scope-definition, Techniques, Material Name, Environmental Conditions, software used)	x	
File and data format	x	
Permalink	x	
Workflow information	x	
Quality Assurance	x	
Access and Licensing (e.g. local, organization server, cloud, public. License, Access Rights, Instructions)	x	
Resources	x	
FAIR-Compliance	x	
Other		

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Table 4: MD use case: FastInMat at CEA

Category	Short description	Additional comment
Title	FastInMat (CEA-DRF/IRAMIS/NIMBE)	
UC-ID	Do not fill (internal use only)	
User Story - primary	Metadata for data sharing (Open & FAIR, sharing across RIs, includes aspects of attribution, interpretability and reproducibility)	Should be made via DIAMOND/DIADEM
User Story - secondary		
Stakeholders: Data source	laboratory experiments (synthesis, characterization)	
Stakeholders: Data provider and host	Institution and datalake	
Stakeholders: Target users	researchers, engineers (advanced materials developers)	
Objectives	Share data with on dedicated repositories	
Primary Operational Context	Experimental/Simulation data (physical units, chemical compositions, measurement quality, etc.)	
Secondary Operational Context		
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (primary)	Materials Science	
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (secondary)	Energy Storage	
Data Characteristics: dataset	raw and processed data	Synthesis parameters (concentration, temperature, gas flowrates, pressure...) and characterization results (chemical composition, size distribution...)
Data Characteristics: presentation	Formatted	tables and datasheets, spectral plots, chemical mapping...
Metadata requirements - check all that apply	General Information (e.g. identification of authorship)	x
	Traceable identifier	x
	Dataset Details (e.g. data source, time-span)	x

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Data source context (e.g. sensor locations, application assets, facility, etc.)	x	
Data processing	x	
Instrumentation, equipment description	x	
Experiment identification: experiment details (e.g. scope-definition, Techniques, Material Name, Environmental Conditions, software used)	x	
File and data format	x	
Permalink		
Workflow information		
Quality Assurance		
Access and Licensing (e.g. local, organization server, cloud, public. License, Access Rights, Instructions)	x	
Resources		
FAIR-Compliance	x	
Other		

Table 5: MD use case: ZEROCARBON at University of Bologna

Category	Short description	Additional comment
Title	ZEROCARBON	low-carbon foot print technologies for the production of advanced materials and the energy transition
UC-ID	Do not fill (internal use only)	
User Story - primary	Metadata for data sharing (Open & FAIR, sharing across RIs, includes aspects of attribution, interpretability and reproducibility)	AMS Acta that is the institutional open access repository
User Story - secondary		
Stakeholders: Data source	Research facilities, laboratory experiments, simulations	
Stakeholders: Data provider and host	University	
Stakeholders: Target users	Other researchers, LCA analysts, advanced materials developers	
Objectives	Open access publications, open data access, promote global data interoperability and collaboration through adherence to FAIR principles.	
Primary Operational Context	Experimental/Simulation data (physical units, chemical compositions, measurement quality, etc.)	
Secondary Operational Context		
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (primary)	Energy Storage	
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (secondary)	Materials Science	
Data Characteristics: dataset	raw and processed data	Example: charts, graphics
Data Characteristics: presentation	txt file, CSV, graphs, charts	
Metadata requirements - check all that apply	General Information (e.g. identification of authorship)	x Experimental user
	Traceable identifier	x
	Dataset Details (e.g. data source, time-span)	x
	Data source context (e.g. sensor locations, application assets, facility, etc.)	x

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Data processing	x	
Instrumentation, equipment description	x	
Experiment identification: experiment details (e.g. scope-definition, Techniques, Material Name, Environmental Conditions, software used)	x	
File and data format	x	CSV
Permalink		
Workflow information		
Quality Assurance		
Access and Licensing (e.g. local, organization server, cloud, public. License, Access Rights, Instructions)	x	
Resources	x	RISEnergy TA access fund
FAIR-Compliance	x	Findability (F3) and Reusability (R1.2)
Other		

D 3.2 - "Use cases and lists of existing metadata platforms and data repositories"

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Table 6: MD use case - H2 at FZJ

Category	Short description	Additional comment
Title	Renewable-based H2 Production and electrolyzer Testing	
UC-ID	Do not fill (internal use only)	
User Story - primary	Metadata for data sharing (Open & FAIR, sharing across RIs, includes aspects of attribution, interpretability and reproducibility)	
User Story - secondary	Metadata for data pipelines (emphasis of semantic interoperability/ontologies, syntactic correctness)	
Stakeholders: Data source	Living Lab Energy Campus (LLEC)	
Stakeholders: Data provider and host	350kW Test station	
Stakeholders: Target users	Integrators, Tech vendors	
Objectives		
Primary Operational Context	Experimental/Simulation data (physical units, chemical compositions, measurement quality, etc.)	Smart grid-integrated renewable energy operations
Secondary Operational Context		
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (primary)	Hydrogen	
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (secondary)	Energy Storage	
Data Characteristics: dataset	PEM Electrolyzer Test data; V2G data; Grid-connected Storage	
Data Characteristics: presentation	Numerical hourly data, stack data	
Metadata requirements - check all that apply	General Information (e.g. identification of authorship)	x
	Traceable identifier	
	Dataset Details (e.g. data source, time-span)	x
	Data source context (e.g. sensor locations, application assets, facility, etc.)	x
	Data processing	x

D 3.2 - "Use cases and lists of existing metadata platforms and data repositories"

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Instrumentation, equipment description		
Experiment identification: experiment details (e.g. scope-definition, Techniques, Material Name, Environmental Conditions, software used)		
File and data format		csv
Permalink		
Workflow information	x	
Quality Assurance	x	
Access and Licensing (e.g. local, organization server, cloud, public. License, Access Rights, Instructions)		
Resources		
FAIR-Compliance	x	
Other		

Table 7: MD use case: SYSLAB at DTU

Category	Short description	Additional comment
Title	FAIR Experiment documentation for SYSLAB experiments	Given any experiment in SYSLAB, a number of data sources need to be selected and combined to a data set. The specific data sources required are specific to the experiment and will always be a small subset of the foundational hundreds of available measurements. Also external 'non-SYSLAB' data need to be included in the dataset to fully capture the experimental data.
UC-ID	Do not fill (internal use only)	
User Story - primary	Metadata for data sharing (Open & FAIR, sharing across RIs, includes aspects of attribution, interpretability and reproducibility)	
User Story - secondary	Metadata for data pipelines (emphasis of semantic interoperability/ontologies, syntactic correctness)	
Stakeholders: Data source	SYSLAB (sensors / instruments in SYSLAB)	
Stakeholders: Data provider and host	DTU, energydata.dk	Could be other, open data host. Energydata.dk doesn't "do" metadata yet.
Stakeholders: Target users	Open: Any researcher interested in the specific experiment result; Closed: Researchers that have been provided with access to the given dataset.	
Objectives	Full interpretability of the experiment data for effective re-use.	
Primary Operational Context	Experimental/Simulation data (physical units, chemical compositions, measurement quality, etc.)	Smart grid-integrated renewable energy operations
Secondary Operational Context	Lab processes (example: experiment design, lab/asset/system configuration)	
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (primary)	Integrated Grids	Energy Storage, Photovoltaics (PV)
RISEnergy focus fields & Target application areas (secondary)	Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	
Data Characteristics: dataset	raw time series data, event log files, experiment design, experiment protocols	

D 3.2 - "Use cases and lists of existing metadata platforms and data repositories"

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Data Characteristics: presentation	CSV or database, text file or time-stamped messages (e.g. JSON text file), design and protocols: unknown - could be document like pdf, or formal structured metadata		
Metadata requirements - check all that apply	General Information (e.g. identification of authorship)	x	
	Traceable identifier	x	
	Dataset Details (e.g. data source, time-span)	x	
	Data source context (e.g. sensor locations, application assets, facility, etc.)	x	
	Data processing	x	
	Instrumentation, equipment description	x	
	Experiment identification: experiment details (e.g. scope-definition, Techniques, Material Name, Environmental Conditions, software used)	x	
	File and data format	x	
	Permalink	x	
	Workflow information		
	Quality Assurance		
	Access and Licensing (e.g. local, organization server, cloud, public. License, Access Rights, Instructions)	x	
	Resources		
	FAIR-Compliance		
Other	x		

3.2 GAP ANALYSIS

It was discovered that, among those responded to the survey, less than 10 out of 84 RIs currently have defined dataset management schemas and even less for their metadata handling. In view of a general lack -partial or total- of MD management plans among a majority of the project members, one can conclude that RISEnergy's metadata service should prioritize the following:

- Analysis of FAIR compliance requirements for RIs and TAs;
- Recommendation for existing data and MD repositories/platforms.
- Development and project-wide standardization of a metadata suitable template;
- Guidelines, examples and other basic training materials to support the adoption of the MD templates to be developed

It is clear that RISEnergy cannot enforce the adoption of a metadata standard into the various RI internal practices, so it will be important to develop an approach that accommodates its gradual adoption and continuous improvement of both the metadata template and associated training materials.

4. EXISTING DATA AND METADATA PLATFORMS

4.1 RATIONALE

A well-organized reference of available **data repositories and metadata platforms** can support researchers of RISEnergy in multiple ways **accelerating and streamlining their research**. By providing **direct access to existing datasets in repositories** and enabling **efficient search and discovery of dataset metadata across platforms**, these resources facilitates identification of **the most impactful pathways** within renewable energy sector for **sharing their own research results** while ensuring data accessibility, interoperability, and reuse in line with FAIR principles.

Each data repository (open or restricted) follows its own standardized metadata and data formats according to its application (data use) context, making it easier to manage and access information. Metadata platforms provide structured, standardized descriptions of datasets, allowing researchers to locate relevant data across various repositories with greater ease.

Some of the expected benefits of these lists may be classified as:

Findable (F)

- **Efficient discovery of existing datasets:** Researchers can quickly locate datasets across multiple repositories without manually searching different platforms.
- **Centralized access to metadata records:** Metadata platforms aggregate structured metadata, making datasets easier to find using standardized search functions.
- **Persistent identifiers (DOIs, ORCIDs, RORs,¹⁶ etc.):** Ensuring that datasets and related research outputs (publications, software, models) are linked and discoverable over time.

Accessible (A)

- **Clear access conditions and licensing information:** Researchers can navigate access policies (open-access, restricted, or require permission) and licensing (e.g., CC BY, CC0).
- **Reliable, long-term availability of data:** By directing researchers to established repositories, they can make their own research data retrievable many years after the project's end.

Interoperable (I)

- **Cross-referencing:** Helps researchers find which repositories **support linking datasets to related outputs** that are relevant to their research activities (e.g., publications, software, models).

¹⁶ <https://ror.org/>

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- **Data integration** (machine actionable): Allow researchers to choose correct (and machine-readable) format formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, NetCDF) for chosen repositories.
- **Cross-disciplinary data linking:** Helps researchers structure their metadata to be compatible with multiple fields' (and repositories) standards, e.g., energy systems, climate science, economics, and facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration

Reusable (R)

- **Minimize duplication:** By making existing datasets easy to find, researchers can reuse existing data and avoid redundant experiments/simulations.
- **Well-structured metadata for long-term use:** Helps researchers structure and document metadata properly to improve long-term usability, making datasets valuable for new analyses beyond their original purpose.

There is a plethora of data repositories, metadata platforms and vocabularies (ontologies) available for energy sciences and technology today. However, they vary widely in terms of data and metadata organization and requirements, intended use, target community, etc.. Such diversity makes it challenging for individual researchers to navigate and determine the most suitable repository with corresponding metadata structure for their research results. Understanding key factors such as submission requirements and FAIR conditions (availability of PIDs, licensing, data formats and metadata, etc.) needs knowledge and expertise that is not readily available to researchers. Aiming address this, a comprehensive lists of data repositories and metadata platforms including these essential details are being compiled to support RISEnergy partners in making informed decisions.

It should be noted that the data repository and metadata platform lists will not only be maintained and updated continuously, but they will be turned into a searchable database for RISEnergy users (i.e., Deliverable D3.6)¹⁷, ultimately accelerating both the scientific progress and the seamless integration of diverse datasets across renewable energy sectors.

4.2 LIST OF DATA REPOSITORIES AND LIST OF METADATA PLATFORMS

The lists of data repositories and metadata platforms are available on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/risenergy/>). Please note that these lists are living documents and will be updated regularly. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the examples of the data repositories and metadata platforms. The attributes identified to describe these data repositories are meant to be informative for characterizing the interoperability of research data repositories, and their compatibility with a targeted FAIR and open research data vision. The list is not meant to be complete, but representative of data repositories relevant for the RISEnergy target renewable energy technology areas.

¹⁷ It is also foreseen to include a list of international and national collaborative projects aiming to establish metadata standards in RE and related sectors.

Repository Name	Website/URL	RISEnergy field	Additional description	Repository Type	Licensing Model	PID Support	Hosting Institution	Submission Requirements
Official name of the data repository	Link to the repository for direct access			Open access / Restricted / Mixed	Default data sharing licenses (e.g., CC BY, CC0, proprietary)	DOI, Handle, or other PIDs for datasets	Organization or funding body managing the repository	Rules for data deposit (e.g., mandatory metadata, embargo options)
Open Energy Information (OpenEI)	https://openei.org/wiki/Main_Page	Renewable Energy - gene	energy-related data, information, analyses, tools, images, and maps for policymakers, researchers, technology investors, and market professionals.	Open	CC0	not specified	NREL	Wikipedia policy
Marine and Hydrokinetic Data Repository (MHKDR)	https://mhkdr.openei.org/home	Ocean Energy,	integrates with PRIMRE (Portal and Repository for Information on Marine Renewable Energy)	Open	DOE-approved or public domain	DOI	NREL	Not suitable for copyright material, business proprietary information, PII
4TU Research Data	https://data.4tu.nl/	Other	a digital repository which support	Open	CC BY 4.0	DOI	TU Delft	metadata list provided. MD stored in RDF. Private link option available
DR POWER Repository	https://egriddata.org/	Integrated Grids,	Generating Realistic Information	Mixed	https://opendefinition.org/	not specified	PNNL & NRECA	Open Data License
Open Energy Data Initiative (OEDI)	https://data.openei.org/	Renewable Energy - gene	Datalake from DoE programs and national labs	Open	CC 4.0		NREL	

Figure 1 Screenshot of the Living table "Data Repositories"

Metadata Platform Name	Website/URL	RISEnergy field	Description	Metadata Standards Used	Persistent Identifier (PID) Support	Integration with Repositories
The official name of the metadata platform.	Direct link to access the metadata platform.	Main RISEnergy research focus		The metadata schema or standards supported by the platform.	The types of persistent identifiers assigned or integrated.	Which repositories or data platforms are compatible with this metadata platform.
EIRIE Metadata Hub	https://www.eirie.eu/	Integrated Grids,	Renewable Energy, Energy System	Dublin Core, INSPIRE, DataCite	DOI, Handle	OpenAIRE, European Commission Energy Data Portals
DataCite, INSPIRE, CKAN	https://datacite.org/ , https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/	Energy, Geospatial Data, Environmental Science, General Research		DataCite, Dublin Core, INSPIRE, Schema.org, DCAT, ISO 19115	DOI, Handle, URN, ARK, ORCID	Zenodo, Figshare, institutional repositories, OpenAIRE

Figure 2 Screenshot of Metadata Repository Sheest

5. FUTURE STRATEGY FOR RISENERGY: METADATA TEMPLATES

A **MD template** should provide a structured and standardized framework to capture relevant details about datasets, experiments, or simulations. It ensures consistency and facilitates data sharing, discoverability, and reuse in compliance with FAIR principles. Furthermore, an acronym list should also be created and encouraged for use so that common terminology is used with a shared meaning.

5.1 MD TEMPLATE CONTENTS - GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

Since there is no complete existing ontology for research infrastructure data sets, the relevant metadata topics have been identified from the perspective of an experienced user. The below presented metadata categories are motivated by both, the "Data Sharing" and the "Data Pipeline" user stories outlined above. To set a background for analysis, consideration was given to the need to describe a dataset from a scientific point of view, considering simulations, field measurements or laboratory experiments as potential dataset origins. Since requirements differ significantly for the different RISEnergy RI areas (e.g. material science vs. ICT, ocean energy devices vs. integrated grids), it is not immediately obvious which concepts can meaningfully be shared across all areas.

1. General Information

- **Title:** A descriptive title of the dataset or research.
- **Description:** Summary of the dataset, its purpose (technology detitanations, e.g., PV, Ocean, H2, etc.), and its context in the research (materials characterization, operation performance...).
- **Keywords:** Relevant keywords for searchability (e.g., "nanomaterials," "solar cells").
- **Unique Identifier:** Persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI or handle) for traceability.

2. Data Creator/Contributor Information

- **Author(s):** Names and affiliations of the researchers.
- **Contact Information:** Email and/or other contact details.
- **TA/VA information**

3. Dataset Details

- **Type of Data:** Experiment or simulation.
- **Material Identifier:** Reference to material database identifiers (e.g., MPID, ICSD, CAS number)
- **Variables/Parameters:**
 - Environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, pressure, humidity).
 - Synthesis details (e.g., precursors, methods, reaction times).
 - Measurement conditions (e.g., spectroscopy setup, beam energy).
- **Spatial/Temporal Coverage:** If applicable (e.g., time-resolved spectroscopy or spatially resolved imaging).
- **System/testing context**
 - Seasonal

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- Physical and networking configuration

4. Experimental/Computational Details

- **Material/System:** Specific material(s) or systems (devices) under study (e.g., composition, phase, or structure).
- **Instrumentation/Tools:** Name, specifications, location and configuration of instruments or software used.
- **Techniques:** Methods applied (e.g., Absorption, electric conductivity, heat capacity, efficiency).
- **Calibration:** Calibration methods or standards used.
- **Software and Version:** Tools and versions (e.g., LAMMPS v1.3).

5. Data & Metadata Format

- **File Formats:** e.g., CSV, JSON, HDF5, or TA/VA-specific formats.
- **Metadata Standards:** Standards used for structuring metadata (e.g., NOMAD for materials science).
- **Data Volume:** Size of the dataset.

6. Workflow

- **Experiment/Workflow ID:** Unique identifier for the experiment or workflow.
- **Steps/Processes:** Description of the procedure or pipeline.
- **Versioning:** Version number of the dataset or workflow.
- **Provenance:** FAIR identification of input data where possible

7. Quality Assurance

- **Validation:** Details on data validation, errors, or uncertainties.
- **Reproducibility:** Information or references to ensure replicability.

8. Access and Licensing

- **Access Rights:** Public, restricted, or embargoed.
- **Licenses:** Creative Commons, MIT, or other licensing terms.
- **Usage Notes:** Specific instructions or disclaimers.

9. FAIR Compliance

- **Findability:** Metadata keywords and search-friendly description.
- **Accessibility:** Persistent identifiers and licensing terms.
- **Interoperability:** Adherence to metadata standards like DCAT-AP or JSON-LD.
- **Reusability:** Rich contextual metadata and validation details.

10. Resources

- **Linked Publications:** Relevant articles or reports.
- **Related Datasets:** Links to other datasets used or generated in the research.
- **Software Links:** Code or script repositories (e.g., GitHub).

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5.2 EXAMPLE MD TEMPLATE

As stated above, the metadata requirements vary significantly across different RISEnergy areas, as well as depending on whether the focus is data sharing or data pipeline integration. The table below presents an example of a possible metadata template for a specific use case in materials science, particularly for X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and computational modelling of materials. The template captures the essential attributes that are among the most commonly required by relevant data repositories, facilitating standardized documentation and interoperability.

Table 8: Example MD template

Field	Description	Example
Title	Name of the dataset	"XRD Analysis of Perovskite Thin Films"
Material Name	Materials studied	"MAPbI ₃ , TiO ₂ "
Instrumentation	Equipment used	"Bruker D8 X-ray Diffractometer"
Environmental Conditions	Conditions during synthesis or testing	"Room temperature, 40% humidity"
Software Used	Computational tools Open source? Free access? Documentation?	"VASP v5.4.1"
File Format	Date type (image, numerical, graphs, video) Format of data	"HDF5, CSV"
Access Rights License Data storage	Public or restricted access Public key is required? Cloud (on prem or public), local server, local desktop	"Open access under CC BY 4.0"

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6. CONCLUSION

The RISEnergy project is committed to supporting its TA/VA to the RIs and users by providing the necessary **cross-RI tools** to enhance their research success. One of the key aspects of this support is to ensure that **data and MD management practices** align with **FAIR principles**, which are essential for accelerating innovation in the renewable energy sector. This report along with Deliverable **D3.1** contribute to this goal by identifying best metadata and data handling practices and guidelines and compiling structured lists of existing data repositories and metadata platforms, and planning the most meaningful 'tools' to be developed within the RISEnergy.

The **critical role of metadata services** is highlighted for ensuring efficient data discovery, interoperability, and reuse. Through a **gap analysis**, the report reveals that many RISEnergy RIs lack standardized metadata management strategies today. To address this, **RISEnergy** will develop **MD templates** and a **searchable database of MD platforms and data repositories** (i.e., Deliverable D3.6). These efforts aim to provide RISEnergy researchers with operational guidance on selecting suitable repositories, applying standardized metadata structures, and ensuring long-term data accessibility and interoperability.

RISEnergy's future efforts will focus on establishing a classification of MD templates that cater to the diverse data needs of the RISEnergy community, and more in general, those of the renewable energy sector, spanning from materials, devices, systems, and to large-scale energy infrastructures. Such templates will align with existing MD standards and best practices to facilitate seamless data integration across the innovation chain. Additionally, by continuing to enrich and refine MD platforms and repository listings, RISEnergy seeks to **accelerate scientific progress, improve data sharing among academia, industry, and policymakers, and enhance the long-term impact of research outputs** in the renewable energy sector.

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